

An Analytical Study on Entrepreneurial Activity as a Tool for Socio- Economic Development of Tribal Women in Kollimalai Hills, Namakkal District in TamilNadu

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Introduction

Entrepreneurship plays an important role in the economic development of a country by taking important inputs from financial, physical, social and infrastructural facilities for progress. Entrepreneurial activity is also important for the development of the tribals who are considered the backward section of the Indian society.

Entrepreneurship plays pivotal role in accelerating the economy, generating employment, eradication of poverty and exploitation of natural resources for the economic development of the country. After the emergence of Liberalisation, Privatisation and Globalisation (LPG) concept the government has shifted its role from job provider to a facilitator of job creator. With this more and more younger people get attracted to undertake entrepreneurial activities for self employment and employment to others also. Entrepreneurial qualities and skills are essential for industrial development as well as eradication of poverty by means of creating self employment and employment to others. The Central and the State governments are trying their best for promotion of entrepreneurship among the economically backward castes, particularly in scheduled tribes through policy measures and institutional network. Keeping in view the need and importance of the entrepreneurship development among underprivileged communities,

The tribal situation in the country presents a varied picture. Some areas have high Tribal concentration while in other areas tribal's have a small portion of the total population. There are some tribal groups, which are still at the food gathering stage, some others practice shifting cultivation, yet other may be pursuing primitive forms of agriculture. Scheduled Tribes (STs) are official designations given to various groups of historically disadvantaged people in India.. In modern literature, the Scheduled Tribes is used as an official term for Adivasis. The Scheduled Tribes comprise about 8.6 percent of India's population according to the 2011 census. The Constitution (Scheduled Tribes) Order, 1950 lists 744 tribes across 22 states in its First Schedule. Since independence, the Scheduled Tribes were given Reservation Status, guaranteeing political representation. The Constitution lays down the general principles of affirmative action for STs. The Constitution of India provides for a comprehensive framework for the socio-economic development of Scheduled Tribes and for preventing their exploitation by other groups of society. A detailed and comprehensive review of the tribal problem was taken on the eve of the Fifth Five Year Plan and the Tribal sub-Plan strategy took note of the fact that an integrated approach to the tribal problems was necessary in terms of their geographic and demographic concentration.

• Origin Of The Research Problem

Ev

en though several studies has been conducted with regard to Socio Economic Development in several District, The most of the studies has been in Western perspective, only limited study has been conducted in Indian Context. Therefore the Researcher intend to fill the gap by Socio-economic upliftment of tribal families through the Employment Opportunity and Encouraging Entrepreneurship among the Scheduled

Tribe Community kollimalai hills in TamilNadu State

• Interdisciplinary relevance

The study will enable the researcher to understand and identify various antecedents of The Constitution of India provides for a comprehensive framework for the socio-economic development of Scheduled Tribes and for preventing their exploitation by other groups of society. This study will helpful in Framing and implementing new

Policy for Employment opportunity and Encouraging Entrepreneurship Among the Tribal People in selected district.

- **Review of Research and Development in the Subject:**

Review Of Literature:

National Status:

Shah (2018) the author concludes that the intersections of cooperation described above have an important general feature. The process of enabling sustainable livelihoods through various interventions is always accompanied by the production of new knowledge while preserving indigenous knowledge. In the last 12 years of activity, the artisans of Tripura not only distributed new technological artifacts, but also those valuable Also accumulated knowledge, scattered across communities, which gave birth to new tribal entrepreneurs.

Singh (2014) the writer states that SMEs play an important role as one of the growth engines of the Indian economy. In fact, they are playing an important role in the socio-economic development of the country, with SMEs prevailing market conditions to facilitate further achievement and streamline objectives related to large scale employment generation, low investment etc, Will need to align its offerings.

Pravesh (2016) in this article the writer states that tribal entrepreneurs are facing many challenges for survival or survival in the competitions market. They do not have the infrastructure facilities to liquefy their business idea or expand the existing enterprise. They are facing financial challenges to start or disseminate their production process. Tribal entrepreneurs have traditional skills and expertise that must be updated with new innovative techniques of production. A networking and exchange system should be promoted by the government or tribal entrepreneurs to exchange their services and consultations between them. Both the central and state governments will be more interested in the promotion and development of tribal entrepreneurship. A separate tribal chamber of commerce should be established by the government or tribal entrepreneurs in the country.

International Status

Tambunan (2019) the authors point out that in the end, the findings of this study are important for policy makers, not only in

Indonesia but also for other developing countries for two main reasons. First, with their vast numbers, MSMEs are indeed very important not only as a source of employment, but, possibly, as an engine of growth for the economy. Second, MSE is a good start for the development of women entrepreneurs. This means that these enterprises have an important role in promoting women empowerment in developing countries, which is one of the important goals of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) these days.

Behera (2018) the auteur states that MSMEs are an integral part of the Indian economy. Major sources of finance used by MSMEs, and we find that most MSMEs use their own capital. MSMEs have faced a situation due to excessive competition from large industries due to withdrawal of subsidies, lack of infrastructure, anti-dumping policy, challenges on product standardization, total quality management etc. by promoting the protection of MSMEs

Kachhal (2017) the book contains several articles about micro, small and medium enterprises that play an important role in the economy of every country. They help to generate employment in an unskilled, semi-skilled and efficient style, at a lower capital cost as these units are basically labor intensive. They also sustain rural economies as many of these products are developed indigenously in rural areas. Products are generally so unique that they offer great potential for export and thus generate revenue in international currency. Due to low production costs and cottage industries like the work environment, they can also hold themselves up during economic instability. The MSME sector has considerable potential and potential to propel the Indian economy. With little support from the government and financial institutions, these units are on course to become pillars of development.

Shivakami (2019) this article has been concluded on the basis of the study and recommends the findings that MSMEs require female entrepreneurs in the areas to increase their market share by focusing on internal marketing competencies for their sustainability Make internal marketing the main factor. Become a member of the marketing avenue and marketing platform created by M / o MSMEs for networking. Create and form an association of MSMEs by

government bodies in the form of networking, referral groups to achieve large scale benefits and improve their industrial relations. Successful women entrepreneurs are encouraged to become mentors and role models because such relationships have a tremendous impact on other women's business successes.

Significance of the study

Tribals have less or no connectivity to the technologies and progress. Their survival was in the forests cutting trees, eating fruits and vegetables. Few were able to come out from the forests for education and exposure to the modern world. Mostly aer suffering due to poverty and cannot provide education generations after generations. They have seen the lowest progress and neglected parts in India. But, after severe hits of pandemic there is a change. The initiative for progressing as "Atmanirbhar Bharat" and NITI aayog accelerated. The remote and indigenous people are now into focus for developing and ensuring entrepreneurship for betterment of the sectors. As a result fruitful employment or activities which can generate more financial resources for the household and improve their financial standing for Tribal People. Therefore, the study becomes necessity.

In his study he has observed the socio-economic status of women entrepreneurs and factors of involvement in micro entrepreneurship and problem faced by them..

(iii) Objectives

1. To Reveal the Socio-Economic Background of the women's entrepreneurship among tribal regions in the Kollimalai Hills in Namakkal districts
2. Analyze the situation (labor and training of women working age located in rural tribes areas in Namakkal districts
3. To examine and Improve the women professional qualifications in rural by organizing a development program.
4. Promote entrepreneurship and the consolidation of business project for women in tribal regions and develop networks of entrepreneurs and business women as a key mechanism of economic revitalization it tribal areas.
5. To measure association between demographic profile of Empower women from rural environments and their

perception on various enterprises started and maintenance of the jobs created .

(iv) Methodology

Research Design:

The proposed study is based on, the composition of both secondary and primary data. The methodology adopted having both descriptive and analytical where both quantitative and qualitative data will be in account. For in-depth analysis, along with Survey method, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) has also adopte keeping in view the qualitative nature of this study. Focus group discussions will be held among the tribal single entrepreneurs and the tribal groups of entrepreneurs. This study is based on field survey and interview method with the tribal entrepreneurs. The present study based on the actual compliance status of different tribal women entrepreneurs use Describe Research Design.

Area of the Study:

The present study is proposed to carryout in Kollimalai Hills in Namakkal district of Tamilnadu.

Universe of Study:

The role for woman empowerment, its changes the living condition of Tribal Hills woman. After starting Enterprises. Tribal women develop their skills, knowledge, and economic conditions, most numbers of woman start many incomes generated business activity because It provide financial support to enhance standard of Living in the Tribal Area. So The Research Select Kollimalai Hills the women started business for more than two years constitute the universe of the study.

Sampling Procedure:

The purposive sampling method will be administrated to collect the data from the Tribal Entrepreneurs. The Namakkal district at Kollimalai Hills will be selected for the study, since this district are predominantly started for Large Numbers of Entrepreneurs.

Selection of Sample Size

The sample size of the Tribal People Entrepreneurial Activity for the present study will be determined by using the following formula

$$n = ((Z * \sigma) / D) ^2$$

Where,

n = number of Sample size,

Z = Z statistics at five percent Significant level,

σ = Standard Deviation of construction workers stress at pilot study,
D = Error of acceptance

Questionnaire Design:

The questions would be framed with special care according to the fulfilment of university grants commission guidelines. The proposed questionnaire consists of three parts. The first part of the questionnaire deals about demographic profile of the Tribal Women,, the second part of the questionnaire consists of variables relating to Various Entrepreneurial activity, the third part of the questionnaire consists of variables relating to impact of income level in tribal women Entrepreneurs.

Number of Questions:

The total number of questions would be around 50 including the demographic profile of the construction workers.

Scaling Techniques:

For constructing questionnaire, five point Likert scale will be administered.

Time needed for Interview:

Thirty minutes is the proposed time for interviewing a respondent.

Pilot Study:

After formulation of the questionnaire, pilot study will be conducted. Based on the feedback received from the respondents, suitable modification will be made in the present study. The questionnaire will be finalized.

Data Sources:

The data would be obtained from two sources. The primary data will be collected from the respondents Existing Tribal Entrepreneurs. They will be interviewed face to face by the researcher adopting interview schedule method. The secondary data will be collected from text books, newspaper, journals and websites.

Method of data processing and tools used for analysis:

The collected data from the respondents will be analysed with the help of SPSS package. In order to identify the various a Entrepreneurial Activity made by tribal people, factors analysis will be administrated. Furthermore, in order to examine the impact of income level of Tribal Entrepreneurs after started Enterprise and Development, multiple regression will be used. The one way ANOVA will be used to find out the significance difference among respondents with different classification of

demographic profile variables and their views on various types of Enterprises started in Tribal area.. Furthermore, cronbach alpha will be used to test the overall reliability of variables included in Socio- Economic Development of Tribal Women Entrepreneurs.

Findings

Findings of the Study Women have played a major and active role in improving the social and economic condition of individual tribal women's in particular and village environment as a whole.

The economically backward tribal women members who are not in the position to provide any collateral security to find the final intuition were benefitted much through the schemes of NGO.

Self help Group After becoming the member of the groups they could borrow bank loans easily without any security. The mode of repayment of the loan is also very convenient.

Financial incentives provided by the Government are easily available and maintain transparency in the same is given due importance.

The regular saving (weakly) habit of tribal women's members has been increased considerably in the study area.

Due to increase in the financial independence the decision making capacity of Tribal women members also increased.

It is proved from the present study that most of the development programmers of Tribal Women supported to socio economic development in rural area is in progress.

Suggestions

The field visit and monitoring are the necessary for the proper maintenance of group activity and from initiating needful corrective measures. Tribal Women to provide proper awareness about the Government scheme in easily way in local language. Recovery approach should be modified. Enough time should be given and stringent action against defaulters should be avoided. In order to strengthen the tribal women empowerment, female literacy has to be promoted rotation of responsibility has to be made compulsory, so that it will lead to tribal women empowerment.

Conclusion

This power or authority can be achieved among these women through reducing poverty, increasing sense of universal

education, improving health awareness and availability of quality nutrition. Along with these there is a necessity in conserving their natural habitat by checking on ecological destruction regularly taking place in their natural home. Empowering may be understood as enabling weaker sections like poor women, especially tribal women to acquire and to possess power and resources, in order to make decisions of their own. Their primitive way of life, economic and social backwardness, and low level of literacy, superstitious believes, out dated system of production and marketing, absence of value systems, scanty physical infrastructure in backward tribal areas and demographic quality of tribal areas show urgency for empowering women. Empowerment is envisaged as an aid to reduce gender gap considerably. Empowerment would enable women to perform social roles, which they cannot perform without it. In the Indian situation

Apart from providing them financial support, they are typing their level best to indulge various interpersonal skills and through proper training programmes they are imbibing to enhance the output with the decreased amount of input. Social security schemes and tribal women empowerment schemes are something which are a very positive step in the ensuring the upliftment of tribal women and providing them proper support to enhance their productivity. Application of the technology in uplifting the society is really appreciated. Hence we can conclude that steps taken by the to start lot of small enterprises in tribal area and enhance and increase the women income level, So the government will take proper steps to start enterprise in Tribal area which needs to be extended for future to ensure helpful results.

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